

Evaluation of the Performance of a Motorised Groundnut Decorticating Machine

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1. INTRODUCTION

Groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea*) or peanut, is an important oil seed and food crop cultivated in semi-arid and subtropical regions of the world. According to Oteng-Frimpong *et al.*, (2017), groundnut is grown on 26.4 million hectare across the world, with a production level of 37.1 million metric tons. Developing countries in Asia, Africa and South America account for over 97% of the global area and 95% of the global production of this crop. China, India, Nigeria, USA and Myanmar are the leading producing countries in the world, while Nigeria ranks highest in West Africa accounting for 51% of production in the region (Ajeigbe *et al.*, 2015).

It is common knowledge that between 1956 and 1967, groundnut was one of Nigeria's most valuable single export crop, evident by the historic Kano groundnut pyramids. The Federal government of Nigeria, through the Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA) is currently working towards restoring these pyramids.

Groundnut is an economic crop in high demand for its wide range of domestic and industrial products. However the kernel has to be separated from its hull before it can be processed; hence decortication is an essential post-harvest operation. Effective decortication is meant to separate the kernel from the hull with no damage to the kernel, which when done manually is time consuming and involves much drudgery.

The most common method of groundnut decorticating in Nigeria is manually by beating the pods in sacks. However several efforts have been made towards motorizing the process, but there is still the challenge of affordability, seed damage and effective seed cleaning. As part of efforts towards producing an effectively suitable motorized groundnut decorticating machine for Nigerian farmers, a model was developed in NCAM. The objective of this work is to test the performance of a model groundnut decorticator developed in NCAM for easy adaptation and possible improvement.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Machine Description

The NCAM motorized groundnut decorticator consists of the following necessary components: the frame, hopper, shelling unit, blower, discharge chute and diesel engine prime mover.

The hopper is trapezoidal in shape with an inclined 520mm long rectangular extension for slide in of the groundnut fruit. It is made with mild steel sheets. The hopper is attached to the shelling drum below it. Inside the shelling drum is an arrangement of 20mm steel beater rods attached to a 50mm shaft for beating the groundnut. A removable 7.5mm screen sieve is fixed at the bottom shelling drum. An inclined rectangular discharge chute at the bottom of the shelling unit has a suction fan connected to its throat.

The beater rods and fan are both connected via a belt pulley arrangement and driven by a 6.5hpa diesel engine.

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Fig.1 Isometric view of groundnut decorticating machine

2.2. Principle of Operation

Dry groundnut pods are fed into the hopper from where they moved by gravity down into the shelling unit. In the shelling unit, they are robed against a fixed concave sieve by rotating members. This robbing action breaks the pods while the shattered pod and seed drop through the sieve-hole. The seed and small broken pieces of pod chaff then travel down across a blower current which is just strong enough to sucks away the chaff. The seed is thereby separated from dirt while cleaned seed proceeds to the delivery chute where it can be collected.

2.3. Design Considerations

The groundnut decorticator was fabricated based on design considerations for optimal performance. The physical and mechanical properties of ground nut species available in Nigeria were strongly considered for proper shelling and kernel and hull separation. This necessitated the use of replaceable sieves with different screen sizes.

Locally available and cost effective materials were also considered for the construction of the machine to ensure affordability and easy maintenance.

Machine factors which include strength, stability, rigidity, power requirement, noise and vibration were suitably considered during machine design and material selection. Operating members were also arranged within recommended ergonomic and safety limits.

2.4. Performance test

The performance test was carried out at the fabrication workshop of the National Center for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM), Ilorin, Nigeria, where the groundnut decorticator was fabricated. SAMNUT - 21(UGA-2) variety of groundnut harvested from Adeyemi Farms located at Balla village, Kwara State was used for the evaluation. The average pod and seed sizes of the groundnut fruit used for this test were 31.59x12.89x11.87mm and 14.55x8.25x7.66mm respectively. The average moisture contents of the groundnut pod and seed were 13.45% and 7.90% respectively.

The test was done in four replicates, during each run 5kg of un-decorticated groundnut fruits were fed into the tested machine. The machine speeds were varied for each of these runs as 146.77, 158.27, 160.5 and 165.27rpm respectively.

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Data were recorded and substituted in the following equations used to calculate evaluated performance parameters;

2.4.1. Input and Output Capacity

a. **Input capacity (I_c):** this is a measure of the quantity of un-decorticated groundnut that can be fed into the decortivating machine in a unit time in kg/hr. The input capacity was obtained from the expression:

$$I_c = \frac{W_u}{t} \quad (1)$$

Where; W_u = weight of un-decorticated groundnut fed into the machine (kg)

t = time taken to decorticate the groundnut (hr)

b. **Output capacity (Q_c):** the weight of decorticated groundnut seed collected at the delivery chute per unit time in kg/hr. This was evaluated from the formulae:

$$Q_c = \frac{W_t}{t} \quad (2)$$

Where; W_t = weight of decorticated groundnut seed (kg)

t = time is taken to decorticate (hr)

2.4.2 Efficiencies

a. **Decortivating efficiency (DE) %:** the decortivating efficiency was obtained from:

$$DE = 100 - \frac{q_c}{G_t} \times 100 = 100 - q_u \quad (3)$$

Where; q_c = weight of cracked seed (kg)

G_t = total weight of seed collected at seed outlet (kg)

q_u = weight of un-decorticated groundnut obtained from the chaff (kg)

b. **Cleaning efficiency (CE) %:** this was evaluated from the formulae;

$$CE = \frac{G_c}{G_t} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

Where; G_c = weight of clear seed collected at seed outlet

2.4.3. Seed loss

a. **Total seed loss (T_L) %:** the total seed loss is the summation of all damages to seed during decortication and it evaluated as follows;

$$T_L = P_u + P_c + c + P_s \quad (5)$$

Where;

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$$P_u \text{ (Percentage un-decorticated seed)} = \frac{q_u}{G_t} \times 100 \quad (6)$$

$$P_c \text{ (Percentage of broken seed)} = \frac{q_c}{G_t} \times 100 \quad (7)$$

$$P_L \text{ (Percentage of clean seed collected at chaff outlet)} = \frac{q_L}{G_t} \times 100 \quad (8)$$

$$P_s \text{ (Percentage of sieve loss)} = \frac{q_s}{G_t} \times 100 \quad (9)$$

Where; q_u , G_t and q_c = as defined in (3)

q_L = weight of clean seed collected at chaff outlet (kg)

q_s = weights of clean seed at (sieve overflow + sieve under flow +stuck seed) kg

2.4.4. Seed Recovery Range

The grain recovery range GRR (%) was determined from the expression;

$$GRR = 100 - P_t \quad (10)$$

Where; P_t = percentage total seed grain losses (%)

2.4.5. Capacity Utilization C_u (%)

This was obtained as follows;

$$C_u = Q_c \times 100 I_c$$

2.4.6. Decortivating Index

The decortivating index (T_i): is the decimal expression of the product of grain recovery range, capacity utilization and decortivating efficiency. It is calculated thus;

$$T_i = GRR \times C_u \times DE$$

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Plate 1: Groundnut decorticating machine during the performance test.

Plate 2: groundnut seed collected at delivery chute Plate 3: chaff of decorticated groundnut

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The result of tests carried out on the motorized decorticating machine is presented in the table.

Table 1. Decortivating efficiency

SN	Test Parameters	A	B	C	D	MEAN
1	Decortivating efficiency DE (%)	100	100	100	100	100
2	Cleaning efficiency CE (%)	90	89.47	94.12	93.75	91.84
3	Un-decorticated P_u (%)	0	0	0	0	0
4	Broken seed P_c (%)	4.65	3.17	4.34	5.31	4.37
5	Blown seed P_c (%)	0.085	0.11	0.059	0.05	0.08
6	Sieve loss P_s (%)	30	52.63	52.94	62.50	49.52
7	Total loss T_L (%)	34.74	55.91	67.86	57.34	53.96
8	Input capacity I_c (kg/h)	326.80	378.79	367.65	381.68	363.73
9	Output capacity Q_c (kg/h)	160	143.90	125	122.14	137.76
10	Seed recovery range GRR (%)	65.26	44.09	32.14	42.66	46.04
11	Capacity utilization C_u (%)	40	38	34	32	36
12	Decortivating index T_i	2610.4	1675.42	1092.76	1365.12	1685.93

It can be observed from the table above that the decortivating machine had an average decortivating efficiency of 100% which confirms that the machine decorticates perfectly. The average cleaning efficiency of 91.84% also shows that adequately cleaned seeds will be collected at the outlet.

On the other hand, the total seed loss averaged at 53%. This is relatively high. However, this was suspected to be as a result of the low angle of inclination of the seed outlet as well as a low feed quantity relative to the high decortivating rate.

The average input and output capacity as shown in the table above were, 363.73kg/h and 137.76kg/h respectively.

The average values of the seed recovery range were 46.04% and capacity utilization 36%. These were low due to the high level of seed loss recorded.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

The performance evaluation of the NCAM Groundnut decorticator revealed that the machine decorticated excellently. The seed was also cleaned to a satisfactory 91.84% level. However the seed loss was high at 53%, which was observed to be likely due to the shallow angle of the shelling drum delivery chute resulting in high seed retention.

The sieve screen size also needs to be better synchronized with the seed and pod size to reduce the sieve loss rate.

If the recommended that adjustments are adequately effected, it is strongly believed that the machine will perform perfectly. This will go a long way to enhance groundnut production and processing in Nigeria coupled with the fact that the machine is affordable and easy to operate.

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